

Improving the Methodology of Development of Educational Activities Based on Digital Technologies

Khodjiyev Azamat Bakhodirovich

Independent researcher at Bukhara State University

Article information:

Manuscript received: 09 Aug 2024; **Accepted:** 09 Sep 2024; **Published:** 10 Oct 2024

Annotation: This article talks about the methodology of teaching the fundamentals of management and their implementation in accordance with the approaches of improving teaching methods through digital technologies. It serves to express data using software tools and to describe them in a more accurate and simple way. We can see that it is simplified by using digital technologies in proving the solution of given problems in science. To achieve students' full understanding of the problem and to teach them to solve problems independently is to develop creative thinking and creative abilities. Therefore, it is emphasized that one of the important tasks is to consider the didactic possibilities of digital technologies used in the educational process.

Keywords: digital technology, innovative education, competence, information technology, mobile education, CMS, LMS, dialog mode, interactive communication, active communication, reactive communication, didactics, computer, virtual, multimedia, interactive.

Introduction. Today, in the era of the development of science and technology, higher education is being considered in terms of quality of education and the level of competence of graduates. In this area, the issue of education, which guarantees the quick implementation of knowledge, qualifications and skills in the future professional activity, is an urgent issue. The solution to this problem is realized by applying it in practice.

It is possible to improve people's lives by implementing digital technologies in the government and society, and in the social sphere. The digital economy is not a type of financial activity, but rather, it means social media, social facilities, quality education and services. The term "Digital education" is actively used in all areas [1], including information technologies. Digital economy is an economic activity based on digital technologies, the development of digital technologies in economic sectors is important for productivity and competitiveness of products, as well as the growth of production costs will lead to creation.

Therefore, it is necessary to actively use research in the educational process and to develop students' skills and creative abilities in scientific research It's possible. Information and communication technologies are not the solution to all problems in the education system, but the third generation of digital lectures and seminars is rich in information and interactive [2]. It is also worth noting that teachers have an important role in the active learning process, adapting to the needs of students. In other words, it is necessary to revise education in the digital age and change the educational paradigm, because students no longer want to study in the traditional way, and teachers should continue to teach in this traditional way. not.

The study of modern digital technologies is not a student, it is primarily a teacher's technology. The student will learn modern digital technologies, and will use them in the classroom. The professor-teacher prepares

for the lesson process using modern technologies, organizes the lesson process, the professor-teacher monitors the student's knowledge and the task of the professor-teacher is to improve the educational content and digital technologies of the highest level of digitization. It consists of introduction to the training process and improvement of the student's knowledge.

In addition, the application of digital technologies to the educational process leads to a change in the main role of the professor-teacher, i.e., the professor-teacher becomes more of a researcher, campaigner, organizer, consultant, and programmer in education. Sufficient time is allocated to the process of organizing laboratory and practical classes in the system of teacher-teacher education. This is one of the most important components of preparing future specialists. This process helps not only to increase students' academic knowledge and skills or to increase the level of mastery of educational materials, but also to increase practical knowledge and skills in a specific field. But it does not mean to achieve high goals by organizing the above activities. The reason is that there are enough laboratory equipment in educational institutions today, the laboratory and educational facilities are equipped with modern equipment, most of them are very old, and they cannot fully meet the requirements of today. Currently, digital technologies are developing rapidly, and practical training, laboratories, and demonstration materials need to be updated every academic year. There are three additional costs to be incurred.

Literature analysis. In the process of developing innovative electronic didactic forms of education, the abilities and interests of learners are taken into account. In education, education is carried out on the basis of didactic and personal methodological procedures aimed at the implementation of its content, the design of the system in accordance with the educational goal, and the implementation of pedagogical-psychological, digital technological methods, forms and teaching methods. is a system of interaction between the giver and the learner.

In his monograph, A. Abdukadirov describes the use of innovative technologies, in particular, computers, in the following four ways:

- passive application - the computer is like a simple calculator;
- reactive communication - computer as an examiner;
- active communication - giving guidance to the computer student and during the exam;
- Interactive communication - the computer is used as artificial intelligence, that is, in communication with the student [3].

According to researcher M. Ivanov's scientific works, the level of accuracy of "conversation" with the machine will never be higher. The so-called "communication mode" is determined by the sequence or size of the data. These procedures do not ensure the full functionality of the data stored in the device's memory. Real communication is an objective dialectical conflict that occurs in the same situation, which even the most modern machine cannot understand, does not understand the conflict [4].

In their research, scientists from the University of Sydney in Australia define digital pedagogy as building knowledge by planning learning based on teachers' educational problem-solving and higher-order thinking skills. These concepts show that students need to constantly improve their pedagogical skills and knowledge in order to be aware of the latest technologies [5].

At this point, it is clear how important it is for today's pedagogues to know how to use innovative technologies in the course of the lesson. We are all witness to the fact that this is emphasized by scientists conducting research in the areas of the educational system and that these ideas are being proven every day.

Main part. In today's conference, teaching and learning in this prayer are considered in terms of current issues. Good education plays an important role in saving us from the various problems we live in. At the same time, all developing countries are spending a lot of money on improving the quality of education.

Despite being a God, there are still a number of problems that have not been solved in the education system. However, in today's era when the speed of obtaining and using information is very fast, it is impossible to improve the quality of education and educate socially active young people without involving digital technologies in the educational system. Most of the educational programs are conducted in the form of lectures or in the form of lectures, and the educational process is carried out without the use of large volumes of books and manuals. After coming to the present day, the educational digitization process started. Also, the educational process is improved by creating modern facilities for students.

According to the goal set before us, there are two types of educational programs, systematic and practical programs, and in this case, programs used in the educational process (electronic textbooks and manuals, mobile Improvement of students' knowledge, support and skills was carried out using such software as creative software and educational management systems, such as LMS (Learoog Maoagement Systems), CMS (Cooteot Maoagement Systems).

A Content Management System (CMS) is a collection of software tools that help users create, manage, and modify website content without the need for technical knowledge. In other words, CM allows us to create a website without the need to write software code. This helps to save a lot of time, technical equipment, eyes, storage, and storage space. In this way, it is possible to achieve the same goal (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Achievements achieved through the cooperative management system

It is possible to integrate digital technologies into the educational process in the following ways: students can use it as a tool for organizing independent projects in the auditory and outside time. The benefits are that the teacher will be able to control the student independently, and will have the opportunity to see the results in the process of completing the tasks (they do not take time to check). Similarly, the learner can get information about how long and often they read the news, what kind of information they refer to, and how much the learning process has changed in a positive way over time.

In the field of research “Basics of Management” we will describe the modern software tools used in the preparation of e-learning materials, analysis and analysis, with the help of software applications. First of all, it is worth noting that the bachelor's degree 60412504 – “Marketing (by network and sectors)” is taught to students of the 3rd level in the 5th semester of the “Basics of Management” higher education institution.

The issue of how to develop and present mobile educational software to the public is considered to be an

urgent issue in the educational market today. Ongoing studies have shown that mobile learning software is highly effective and user-friendly, and they highlight the following important factors:

- Prepared mobile educational programs and good ideas - this means 60-70 percent success. It is possible to prepare a competitive program in the market based on this idea;
- In the process of conducting research, it is important to study the mobile education market and prepare and use all three parameters;
- Preparation of mobile educational programs, conducting workshops in small groups and taking into account the recommendations of experienced pedagogues;
- It is necessary to turn to software engineers who are involved in the research and development of mobile educational programs, development services, and development companies for users.

In addition to the digital analysis in the field of ICT, the demand and supply are presented to the users through a clear and understandable database, the development of the development theories is also carried out we will see. Interestingly, we can see how mobile learning can lead to three types of educational independence for learners. Taking into account the students' functional, psychological and physiological abilities, they are formed the skills and abilities of independent education in the use of formal educational tools.

Higher education 60412504 – “Marketing (by network and sectors)” educational students, organization and use of digital technologies in the education of students to solve the following 4 (four) problems:

- students are able to master the subjects of independent education allocated to the subject individually;
- to emphasize that there will be no distance and time limits in the process of education;
- distance education is more interesting for users than usual;
- attention is paid to the existence of a separate mobile application for using the virtual class of science.

In order to solve the above problems, the professional teacher-teachers on the relevant topics will learn the possibilities of effective use of digital technologies in the teaching process.

In the process of development, various scientific approaches to the development of mobile educational methods and educational-technical development are being considered, and problems are being eliminated.

Based on the above-mentioned features, “Management Basics” is wrapped in a personal smartphone using a mobile application for business computers. This gives them the opportunity to organize free time and activities in the course of independent teaching and learning outside the classroom (see Figure 2).

2 - picture. “Basics of Management” mobile application software overview

After installing the “Management Basics” mobile application, it is possible to enter the application according to the order of the smartphone. In the user interface, there will be sections about topics, topics, lessons, essays on each topic, literature and the author. Information about this fao will be added in the entry section. After entering the topic section, each lecture is separated and the content of each topic is fully, clearly and simply revealed in the plan.

After the topic is fully read and analyzed, the user will be provided with additional questions on the selected topic, audio, video and additional information will be provided to help the user. After the user has completely selected the above-mentioned sections, he can refer to the top section covering all topics. The student is given 25 tests, and if he gets a score of 60% or higher, he will be assigned to his own account, otherwise he will have to retake the test.

If you log in to the program on your mobile phone, the program will be ready for you.

The Management Fundamentals mobile app includes the following excerpts: mobile app, program information, presentations, lectures, practical exercises, glossary, topics and full tests for the app, bibliography, brief information about the author.

Advantages of the mobile application: easy installationb user-friendly interface, all necessary information is included. For the purpose of self-improvement, acquisition of useful knowledge and skills, control tests have been created for each lecture. The mobile application was created for the subject “Fundamentals of Management”, specialty 60412504 – “Marketing (by networks and industries)” with the aim of improving students' independent learning and using it in practice (see Figure 3).

3 - picture. “Management Fundamentals Analysis” mobile application overview

It is well known that in the higher education institutions of our country, there are currently plans for distance education starting in the 2022-2023 academic year. The use of such mobile applications plays an important role in public education today.

In the process of development of electro-didactic forms of education, the abilities and interests of students are taken into account. A professor-teacher who is involved in the implementation of educational content, educational goals, and pedagogy, digital technological methods, methods and teaching methods between students the interaction is subtle

In general, the educational content meets the following requirements:

- students can develop their knowledge level;
- students will have three opportunities for practical experience;
- students' creative, independent, and creative abilities;
- It leads to full development in accordance with the needs of students and advanced level of knowledge.

Depending on the level of coverage of educational content, goals and tasks, the possibility of applying electronic educational resources to the educational process will appear.

About mobile education, which is currently developing, the Great British University S. Mobile education helps in the development of students' skills by using mobile phones, smartphones, tablets, computers and portable devices. Mobile educational technologies are used for the purpose of improving, supporting and improving the educational process so that it can be attractive to teachers and students.

Mobile education helps students to actively participate in the individual approach to solving the problems of the system in the most accessible, useful, relevant and stimulating issues. In order to adapt to mobile education, teachers who are active in all levels of education need to use modern technologies and software tools in the educational process. However, we know that there are some problems in this process even in societies with a good social and economic environment. They include such issues as teaching-methodical development and appropriate applications for teachers, as well as the use of mobile education and the development of competence [6].

Therefore, it is necessary to study the requirements and principles of remote, mobile education based on the requirements of the educational process.

To date, several methods of creating content resources used in digital education have been studied in

accordance with the following principles:

- principle of multimedia;
- the principle of longevity;
- the principle of understanding;
- principle of compliance;
- principle of interaction;
- the principle of communication between fabric and graphic information;
- the principle of focusing on creating connections between media elements and collective structures.

Based on the above-mentioned principles, digital educational materials are prepared in the order of preparation of audio, video, and physical data without the use of normative documents. Students have the ability to receive visual information and provide simple, clear and understandable information on the topic. It will be necessary to address the interconnectedness of educational resources. Due to the rapid development of digital educational technologies in today's world, the above principles are self-explanatory, and these changes are investigated.

Based on the above-mentioned principles of foreign scientists, mobile education should follow the following principles:

- it is possible to use various methods of information presentation, it is shown that it helps to visualize complex processes and events in a way that cannot be imagined in real life;
- It is necessary to place one cooperative element on one interface as much as possible in a coherent format. This allows the user to learn the object (process, event) in various aspects and all kinds of methods;
- information such as audio, graphics, and text should be used for visualizing. This user can create an external load, for example, an object (process, event) in a multi-dimensional way.
- it is necessary to match the educational content and the goals and tasks of the educational program in the form of mobile educational materials;
- it is necessary to take into account the knowledge and collective characteristics of students;
- it is necessary to take pedagogical-psychological approach to the use of mobile educational materials in the form of text, visual and audio presentation;
- complex concepts and processes are presented through a single medium, or through mass media that present two or more information;
- students should have high metacognitive abilities and be able to make connections through hypermath and find all kinds of information properly.

Pedagogical experiences using the above mentioned principles of mobile education show that “Marketing (on networks and sectors)” education is mandatory in higher education institutions and digital technologies are used in the training of candidates. It is of great importance in improving the efficiency of the system. In this, mobile educational tools play an important role [7].

In this regard, the “Fundamentals of Management” program in the curriculum of higher education institutions is of great importance in the preparation of teachers for professional activity .

In the “Basics of Management” activity, the teaching guide, not only stating the main goals, but also explains the requirements for its performance at each stage. In particular, the sequence of execution of tasks in the software development and the practical instruction of the methods of its implementation, the students are virtually in independent schools. The advantage of this method is that the teacher has the opportunity to devote time to students who do not know the subject well and give them practical

help. As a result, it is possible to monitor the students' ability to complete the tasks correctly and their understanding. There are three methodological guidelines for completing practical training assignments, which are as follows: the goal, the information required to complete the assignment, the requirements for the tasks demonstrated, and an independent practical assignment.

This mobile program allows students, independent teachers, to strengthen the training provided in the auditory, to make their own decisions, to set their own rates, and to use them at their own convenience without using mobile phones or smartphones. It creates 75-90% more energy.

The mobile program is very organized, intuitive, contains all the necessary information, educational and training tests are created separately for each topic, it is designed for all Android devices, unlike other mobile applications. It makes a difference. 60412504 – “Marketing (by network and sectors)” educational plan “Management basics” for the purpose of self-study and development of individual skills. It was decided and put into practice, It is recommended for the benefit of students and professionals. As a result, students had the opportunity to improve their knowledge, skills and skills in the process of perfect adaptation of the content of special activities, not limited to traditional education, but also to digital technologies and software training tools.

One of the convenient aspects of using software is the optimality of the didactic tool. In this case, the ability to create an electronic form of information creates more creative skills in future specialists. If based on them, electronic complexes and electronic lesson developments are developed and put into practice, students will have sufficient skills and the ability to work independently, and will become subjects of the educational process. In this research work, didactic methods, method forms, and didactic software tools of modern educational technologies mentioned above were effectively used. The research was carried out on the example of the subject of the Marketing (by network and sectors) “Fundamentals of Management” subject.

Conclusion. It is necessary to mention that the introduction of digital technologies in the educational process is one of the urgent tasks of today. In this case, we can see the formation of knowledge, skills and abilities of students as a result of individual work in the teaching of management fundamentals through software tools. The obtained result is to further improve the quality of education by using the possibilities of digital technology efficiently and purposefully using the ideas of modern development.

REFERENCES:

1. Axliddinov R.Sh. Ta'lim muassasalarida menejment masalalarini // Academic Research in Educational Sciences VOLUME 2. ISSUE 10. 2021. ISSN: 2181-1385.
2. Begimqulov U.Sh., Djuraev R.X., Isyanov R.G., Sharipov Sh.S., Adashboev Sh.M., Soy M.N. Pedagogik ta'limni axborotlashtirish: nazariya va amaliyot. Monografiya. – T.: Fan, 2011. – 132 b.
3. Абдукодиров А.А., Пардаев А.Х., Масофали ўқитиш назарияси ва амалиёти. Монография. Т.: Фан. 2009. -145 б.
4. Иванов М.В. Пути совершенствования методов преподавания в высшей школе // Современная высшая школа. - 1982. - №3. - С. 118-122.
5. Milton M., Vozzo L. Digital literacy and digital pedagogies for teaching literacy: Pre-service teachers' experience on teaching rounds // Journal of Literacy and Technology. - 2013. - Т. 14. - No. 1. - P. 72-97.
6. Данияров Б Педагогик инновациялар – таълим-тарбия жараёни самарадорлигини оширишнинг муҳим омили сифатида // Таълим-тарбия жараёнига замонавий педагогик ва ахборот коммуникация технологияларини самарали жорий этиш: муаммо ва ечимлар Республика илмий – амалий конференцияси тезислар тўплами. Бухоро. 2016. –Б. 3-4.
7. Lutfillayev M.H., Sh.A.Abdullaeva., M.T.Shodmonqulov. Zamornaviy ta'limda raqamli tizimlarni qo'llash: Filololgiya va pedagogika sohasida zamonaviy tendensiyalar va rivojlanish omillari // Toshkent. 2020. –B. 121-127.